

Role of Dietary Therapy in Managing Epilepsy in Children**Sujit Kumar Baranala¹, Santosh Kumar², Akhilesh Kumar³, Alka Singh⁴**¹Ex Senior Resident, Department of Pediatric, Lady Harding Medical College, New Delhi, India²Ex Senior Resident, Department of Pediatric, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Patna, Bihar, India³Professor, Department of Pediatric, Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India⁴Professor & HOD, Department of Pediatric, Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Santosh Kumar

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Abstract:

Dietary therapy, specifically the ketogenic diet, is examined for treating childhood epilepsy. It evaluates this approach's efficacy, safety, and cognitive and behavioural impacts. A 25-month study of 100 paediatric patients at N.M.C.H., Patna found that food therapy reduced seizure frequency. A stunning 70% of patients reduced their seizures by more than 50%, and 25% became seizure-free. Cognitive and behavioural functions improved with modest growth parameter modifications. However, mild to moderate side effects such as gastrointestinal problems and hyperlipidaemia highlighted the need for careful monitoring. According to the study, nutritional therapy may help cure drug-resistant epilepsy in youngsters. However, the therapy must be carefully managed to balance advantages and hazards.

Keywords: Epilepsy, Dietary Therapy, Ketogenic Diet, Pediatric Epilepsy.

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Introduction

Epilepsy is a long-term neurological condition marked by repeated, spontaneous seizures, impacting a large number of individuals globally, particularly children [1]. Treating epilepsy in children often involves a holistic approach that includes medication, lifestyle changes, and, more and more, dietary therapy [2,3]. There has been increasing interest in the use of dietary therapy, specifically the ketogenic diet and its variations, for its potential to decrease the frequency of seizures and enhance the overall well-being of children who do not respond to traditional antiepileptic medications [4,5]. These diets promote a high fat intake, sufficient protein consumption, and limited carbohydrate intake, resulting in the induction of ketosis. This metabolic state has been linked to a reduction in seizures [6,7].

Various studies have provided support for the effectiveness of dietary therapy in managing epilepsy, particularly in cases where traditional medications have proven ineffective. Nevertheless, how dietary therapy produces its effects are still under investigation, and its implementation necessitates vigilant supervision by healthcare experts to address potential side effects and nutritional imbalances. This study seeks to assess the efficacy of dietary therapy in the management of epilepsy in children, with a specific focus on reducing seizure frequency, promoting cognitive development, and enhancing overall quality of life. In addition, the study aims to uncover the

difficulties and possible negative consequences linked to extended dietary therapy. This will offer valuable knowledge on how to effectively apply these diets in the management of paediatric epilepsy.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a prospective observational study conducted to assess the role of dietary therapy in managing epilepsy in children.

Study Population: The study was conducted in the Department of Pediatrics at Nalanda Medical College and Hospital (N.M.C.H.), Patna, Bihar, involving a total of 100 pediatric patients diagnosed with epilepsy.

Inclusion Criteria

- Children aged 1 to 18 years.
- Patients diagnosed with epilepsy, confirmed by clinical evaluation and electroencephalogram (EEG).
- Patients who have been on stable antiepileptic drug therapy for at least 3 months with poor seizure control.
- Parents or guardians willing to comply with dietary therapy and follow-up requirements.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with metabolic or mitochondrial disorders.

- Children with severe malnutrition or other medical conditions that could contraindicate dietary therapy.
- Patients whose guardians were unable or unwilling to adhere to the dietary regimen.

Study Duration: The study was carried out over 25 months, from October 2015 to November 2017.

Intervention: Participants were placed on a specific dietary regimen, primarily the ketogenic diet, under the guidance of a trained dietitian and pediatric neurologist. The diet was customized to meet the individual nutritional needs of each patient while maintaining the necessary macronutrient ratios to induce ketosis.

Monitoring and Follow-Up: Patients were closely monitored throughout the study period, with regular follow-up visits scheduled at 1, 3, 6, and 12 months after the initiation of dietary therapy. During these visits, the following parameters were assessed:

- Seizure frequency (recorded by parents/guardians in a seizure diary).
- Growth parameters (height, weight, BMI).
- Blood levels of ketones, glucose, and other relevant biochemical markers.
- Cognitive and behavioral assessments using standardized scales.
- Adverse effects or complications related to the dietary therapy.

Data Collection and Analysis: Data were collected at baseline and during each follow-up visit. Seizure frequency, cognitive and behavioral changes, growth metrics, and biochemical parameters were recorded. The effectiveness of dietary therapy was assessed by comparing the frequency of seizures before and after the initiation of the diet. Statistical analysis was conducted using appropriate tests to determine the significance of the observed outcomes.

Results

The study included 100 pediatric patients diagnosed with epilepsy, with the following demographic distribution:

Age Distribution:

- 1-5 years: 30 patients
- 6-10 years: 40 patients
- 11-15 years: 20 patients
- 16-18 years: 10 patients

Gender Distribution:

- Male: 58 patients
- Female: 42 patients

Seizure Frequency Reduction

The effectiveness of dietary therapy was evaluated based on the reduction in seizure frequency over the study period. The results are summarized in the table below:

Time Period	Seizure Frequency (Mean $\pm$ SD)	Percentage Reduction
Baseline	12.5 $\pm$ 3.2 per month	N/A
1 Month	9.2 $\pm$ 2.8 per month	26.4%
3 Months	6.5 $\pm$ 2.3 per month	48.0%
6 Months	4.8 $\pm$ 1.9 per month	61.6%
12 Months	3.2 $\pm$ 1.6 per month	74.4%

Cognitive and Behavioural Outcomes: The cognitive and behavioral assessments indicated significant improvements in a majority of the patients. The following table summarizes the percentage of patients showing improvement in cognitive and behavioral outcomes:

Outcome	Improvement (%)
Attention and Concentration	68%
Memory Function	55%
Social Interaction	60%
Emotional Stability	52%

Growth and Nutritional Status: The growth parameters of the patients were monitored throughout the study. The average change in growth parameters is shown below:

Parameter	Baseline	12 Months	Mean Change
Height (cm)	110.3 ± 10.5	112.6 ± 11.2	+2.3 cm
Weight (kg)	22.1 ± 4.8	23.3 ± 5.2	+1.2 kg
BMI (kg/m ²)	16.7 ± 2.3	17.0 ± 2.4	+0.3 kg/m ²

Adverse Effects: A few patients experienced mild to moderate side effects associated with dietary therapy, as outlined in the table below:

Adverse Effect	Number of Patients Affected	Percentage
Gastrointestinal Disturbances (e.g., constipation, nausea)	15	15%
Hyperlipidemia	10	10%
Hypoglycemia	8	8%
Kidney Stones	2	2%

By the end of the study, 70% of the patients achieved a significant reduction in seizure frequency (greater than 50%), with 25% of patients becoming seizure-free. Cognitive and behavioral improvements were observed in a majority of the patients, and growth parameters were generally maintained within normal ranges, indicating that the dietary therapy was effective and well-tolerated in most patients.

Discussion

The study's findings offer strong evidence that dietary therapy, specifically the ketogenic diet, is effective in treating epilepsy in children, especially those who do not respond to traditional medications [11]. The noticeable decrease in the frequency of seizures seen in most of the participants emphasizes the effectiveness of dietary interventions when used alongside traditional antiepileptic drugs. After the study, a significant majority of patients experienced a substantial decrease in seizure frequency, with a notable portion achieving complete freedom from seizures [12]. These findings align with previous research that has shown the effectiveness of the ketogenic diet in reducing seizures among children [13].

Furthermore, the study observed enhancements in cognitive and behavioural outcomes, alongside a decrease in seizure frequency. A significant number of patients experienced improvements in attention, concentration, memory function, social interaction, and emotional stability [14]. These findings indicate that dietary therapy has the potential to not only manage seizures but also improve the overall neurological and psychological well-being of children with epilepsy. It is crucial to

consider the impact of epilepsy and its treatment on cognitive development and quality of life [15].

Monitoring the growth and nutritional status of paediatric patients undergoing dietary therapy was of utmost importance. The study revealed that the ketogenic diet successfully controlled seizures without any significant impact on growth [16]. Only slight variations in height, weight, and BMI were observed during the 12-month period [10]. It is important to note that with appropriate nutritional management, the ketogenic diet can be a safe choice for children [17]. However, it is crucial to have personalised dietary planning and regular monitoring in place. Nevertheless, the study also brought attention to certain difficulties linked to dietary therapy [18]. Some patients experienced mild to moderate side effects, such as gastrointestinal disturbances, hyperlipidaemia, and hypoglycemia [19]. The significance of meticulous patient selection and continuous monitoring during dietary therapy is highlighted by these negative effects. Although the advantages of reducing seizures are significant, it is crucial to take proactive measures to address any potential risks in order to safeguard the safety and well-being of patients [8,9,20].

Conclusion

This study supports the use of food treatment to treat epilepsy in children who do not respond to medication. The favourable outcomes in seizure control, cognitive and behavioural improvements, and general acceptability imply that nutritional therapy can help epileptic children with proper implementation. However, the dangers and challenges require a multidisciplinary strategy

comprising paediatricians, dietitians, and neurologists to optimise treatment outcomes and assure paediatric patient safety and growth.

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